

DEVELOPING ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNERS' MOTIVATION THROUGH GAMES

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ABSTRACT

The article reveals the role of games in the process of teaching a foreign language. The use of games in teaching a foreign language develops the skills of dialogue speech and communication, develops the oral initiatives of students and strengthens the natural communicative orientation of the lesson. Many educators and authors assume that when learning through games, students unconsciously memorize new lexical and grammatical material. Thus, the use of games in teaching a foreign language is one of the most effective ways that gives students the opportunity to speak and at the same time motivates them.

Keywords: vocabulary games, the role of games in language teaching, the use of language games, types of language games, techniques of teaching vocabulary.

АҒЫЛШЫН ТІЛІН ҮЙРЕНУГЕ АРНАЛҒАН МОБИЛЬДІ ҚОСЫМШАЛАР

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АҢДАТПА

Мақалада шетел тілін оқыту процесіндегі ойындардың рөлі сипатталған. Сөздік дағдыларды оқытуда ойындарды қолдану оқушының диалогтық сөйлеу дағдылары мен коммуникативтік дағдыларын дамытады, оқушылардың еркін сөйлеуіне бастама болады және сабақтың табиғи коммуникативтік бағытын арттырады. Авторлар ойын арқылы оқыту кезінде оқушылар еріксіз түрде жаңа лексикалық және грамматикалық материалдарды жаттайды деп болжайды.

Сонымен қатар, шетел тілін оқытуда ойындарды қолдану оқушылардың сөйлеу мүмкіндіктерін ашатын және оларды ынталандыратын тиімді әдістердің бірі болып табылады.

Кілт сөздері: сөздік ойындар, тілді оқытудағы ойындардың рөлі, тілдік ойындарды қолдану, тілдік ойын түрлері, сөздерді оқыту әдістемелері.

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ МОТИВАЦИЯ УЧАЩИХСЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА С ПОМОЩЬЮ ИГР

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье раскрывается роль игр в процессе обучения иностранному языку. Использование игр при обучении словарным навыкам развивает привычки и навыки диалоговой речи, способствует развитию устной инициативы учащихся и усиливает естественную коммуникативную направленность урока. Авторы предполагают, что учащиеся, играя в игры, непроизвольно запоминают новый лексический и грамматический материал. Таким образом, использование игр в обучении иностранному языку является одним из наиболее эффективных способов, которые дают учащимся возможность говорить и в то же время мотивируют их.

Ключевые слова: словарные игры, роль игр в обучении языку, использование языковых игр, виды языковых игр, методы обучения лексики.

Nowadays teachers often struggle the problem of arousing an interest of students while teaching them. It often happens that when traditional methods of teaching are ineffective and do not arouse student's interest. This problem often arises while teaching foreign languages, when working with teenagers. In elementary school, the method of teaching lessons includes the use of various funny songs, games, etc. But in adolescence, students lose interest in such methods, and the number of methods corresponding to the interests of students becomes more complicated. Currently, you can notice the problem of increased stress during training with students. Using a variety of games while teaching helps reduce the stress on students. When using game forms, the student unconsciously acquires the educational material. We believe that playing a

game is a very effective method and especially it helps to reveal the hidden abilities of a person, in particular a child. Games have long been promoted as an aid to language learning. Here are some of the reasons why: Games increase interest in things that students may not find very interesting.

1. Maintaining interest can mean constant effort. After all, learning a language takes a lot of effort.
2. Games provide a context for constructive communication. This meaningful communication provides the basis for intelligible input, that is, what students understand when they listen and read, interactions to increase comprehensibility, such as asking for repetition or examples and a clear result, speaking writing so that others can understand.
3. The variety and intensity of games can reduce anxiety and awaken interest and activity in more shy students.
4. When using games, all the basic language learning skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing can be incorporated, and different are often involved in a single game. To achieve the aforementioned benefits, we need to think about when and how to use games. Games can play different roles in a language program. Usually, in traditional forms of teaching games are used as a warm-up at the beginning of the lesson, or as an additional task if there is a free time, or as an addition to the lesson diversify the curriculum [1,56].

Play is a purposefully organized activity that requires active participation and focused use of emotional and mental strength. The game always presents a specific problem “how to win?” The desire to win and to solve problems contributes to the development of the student’s mental activity. Let’s highlight the goals of using games in foreign language lessons. There are six main goals:

1. Development and formation of certain language skills such as listening, reading, vocabulary, etc.;
2. Growth of certain speech skills;
3. improving the ability to communicate, work with society;
4. extension of the necessary abilities and mental functions;
5. cognition (in the sphere of the formation of the language itself);
6. fast and effective memorization of speech material.

The game is significant also for personal growth, because during the game process a certain situation is created in which the student wants to help his team win out in the game and participates very actively. As practice shows, in such situations, not only strong students participate actively, but also weak students show activity and diligence. Very often, students with low grades can demonstrate their skills through play, contribute to the victory and be active. Therefore, the use of games can be a good method for teaching weaker and shy children, to awaken their activity and interest in

the subject and become the basis and motivation for learning the language. Why should we use games in class time?

- They are funny and most of the students like to play them. Through games students experiment, discover, and communicate with the others.

- Games add variety and motivation to the lesson, creating a good reason to use the target language.

- The context of the game makes a foreign language indispensable for children. This brings the target language to life.

- The game makes the reasons for conversation understandable even for stubborn students.

- By playing games, students can learn English in the same way that children learn their own language without knowing what they are learning; so they can learn a lot without stress [2,45].

When to use games? Usually, in traditional forms of teaching games are used as a warm-up at the beginning of the lesson, or as an additional task if there is a free time, or as an addition to the lesson diversify the curriculum. According to the Lee, a game “should not be regarded as a marginal activity filling in odd moments when the teacher and class have nothing better to do”. Games should be at the heart of teaching foreign languages. Rixon observes that games should be used at all steps of the lesson program, provided that they are suitable and carefully chosen. At different stages of the lesson, the teacher’s aims connected with a game may vary:

1. Presentation. Provide a good model making its meaning clear;

2. Controlled practice. Elicit good imitation of new language and appropriate responses;

3. Communicative practice. Give students a chance to use the language [3,84].

How to Choose Games?

- A game must be more than just fun.
- A game should involve “friendly” competition.
- A game should keep all of the students involved and interested.
- A game should encourage students to focus on the use of language rather than on the language itself.

- A game should give students a chance to learn, practice, or review specific language material [4,30].

In addition to defining the role of games in learning, we also need to know the classification of games. According to S.V. Kulnevich and T.P. Lakotsenina we may classify games into these categories: Games-exercises: This category include different kind of puzzles, quizzes, charades, crosswords, explaining the meaning of proverbs sayings and etc. Travel Games: Travel games include a variety of oral stories, question-

and-answer assignments, discussions about personal experiences and students' judgements. Travel games can be both conducted as a classroom activity and as an extracurricular activity. The storyline (role-playing) game is an improvisation game in which students act out various dialogues and scenes, such games help to improve the student's imagination and speech activity [5,67].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Research in the research work applied the method of lexical comparative analysis. In addition, methods of analysis, examination and analysis of historical, lexical and grammatical analysis methods of analysis, examination and analysis of historical, social, language, professional, Jargon and other spheres, including introductory words, were taken as a basis. The opinion of scientists on the given industries was used as the main quote. For analysis, information on the different types of games activities gain to effective ways of learning language learning of the language, lexicology, the history of the English language, etc. were taken into account.

The second type of game classification that Hadfield uses has a much larger category:

1. Sorting, ordering, or arranging games. For instance, students have a set of cards or a drawing with different meanings students must sort them into specific groups that combine the words.

2. Information gap games. In this game, one group of students have certain information that other participants need to complete the assignment.

3. Guessing games. These are a variation on information gap games. One of the well-known examples of a guessing game is 15 Questions, in which one student thinks about certain things but does not tell their class such as a famous person, place or something. Other participants should ask 15 yes / no questions and, based on the answers, should guess who or what the person is thinking.

4. Search games. These games are another variation of information-gap games in which everyone has to give and seek information.

5. Matching games. As the name suggests, students must match a word, picture, or card. This game can be organized both individually and in groups.

6. Labeling games. These are a form of matching, in that students match labels and pictures.

7. Exchanging games. In these games, students barter cards, other objects, or ideas. Similar are exchanging and collecting games. Many card games fall into this category, such as the children's card game.

8. Board games. Scrabble is one of the most popular board games that specifically highlights language.

9. Role play games. The terms role play, drama, and simulation are sometimes used interchangeably but can be differentiated. Role play can involve students playing roles that they do not play in real life, such as dentist, while simulations can involve students performing roles that they already play in real life or might be likely to play, such as customer at a restaurant [6,88].

The introduction of various games into the process of learning a foreign language, namely to develop vocabulary skills, develops habits and the ability to conduct a dialogue speech more and more, contributes to the progress of the active oral desire of students and increases the inherent communicative orientation of the lesson. The creators admit that in the process of playing the student instinctively memorize new lexical and grammatical information. From which it should be understood that the use of games in teaching a foreign language is one of the effective methods that encourage and give more resources to students. In learning a foreign language, one of the most important parts is vocabulary. This factor brings together four core skills: reading, writing, speaking and listening. To have high-quality communication with people in a foreign language, you need to know more words, that is, a rich vocabulary, and it is also very important to be able to use these words correctly. Gairns and Redman offer the following group of techniques for introducing new words:

1. Visual techniques. Visual techniques are very effective as they relate to visual memory which is the most durable. Pupils remember well the material which is demonstrated with the help of visual examples and manuals. This technique is convenient to use with groups of words that belong to the same category as nouns. 2. Verbal explanation. This technique refers to the use of illustrative situations and action, explanation using synonyms or opposites.

3. Using dictionaries. Using a vocabulary is also an effective memorization method. Students can search for the meaning or translation of words and phrases in various dictionaries: monolingual dictionaries, dictionaries with synonyms, thematic dictionaries, graphic dictionaries etc [7,102].

In order to expand vocabulary you need a media. One of them is the game. Games are a way to have fun. The use of games can influence students in a positive way, making them more focused on the lesson, the feeling of being forced to be present in the classroom disappears. Also, games reduce feelings of anxiety, self-doubt, while increasing the possibility of gaining more knowledge. Using games during the lesson can help shy and inactive students to take the initiative in learning a foreign language and a desire to express their thoughts and feelings. Allows students to gain more experience than in the course of a regular lesson. The use of games encourages students to actively participate in the lesson as it is fun, easy communication with which

students feel free. They can experiment, try to cooperate and improve relations with the environment. Now let's look at the games that we can use during the lessons.

1. Word association. Students must name all words they know that belong to any lexical category. One student pronounces a word from a certain class, then the next student must pronounce a word that is included in this class. The next student continues to speak another word, and so on throughout the class. For example, for the Health category, the game might go like this: Student 1: Student disease 2: catch cold student 3: sneeze Student 4: cough Student 5: medicine The student who cannot continue the chain of words drops out of the game.

2. Memory game. In this game, the first student begins by pronouncing any sentence, then the second student must add one word or phrase repeating the sentence that was said earlier. For instance: Student 1: I woke up at 6 am. Student 2: I woke up at 6 am and did the exercises. Student 3: I woke up at 6 a.m. did the exercises and made myself breakfast. This continues until someone can repeat everything said or can not add something to the sentence, the one who cannot do this drops out of the game.

This game helps improve memory and builds vocabulary.

3. Miming can be used as a guessing game. This game helps students to speak freely and naturally, the main rule is to use only the language being studied. One of the students simulates explaining one thing or action, other students must guess what it is, while guessing, students can ask a little hint, For example, if this is an animal, then you can ask "Does this animal fly?" or "Does this animal live on dry land?" etc. This game helps to quickly memorize information and learn words, which will then be remembered for a long time.

4. Guess the tool game is a good opportunity to develop students' skills in identifying words and paraphrasing. This game can be organized as a pair or group work. In pair work, the teacher gives each student a card with words, students should not show their words, then they need to take turns explaining what kind of word is written on the card without using the word itself. For example: Student 1: This thing is used to create paintings, also a brush is used in conjunction with this thing. To sum up, I would like to indicate, in fact, that games are effective work as a way to update vocabulary supplies. Students also love games and puzzles in other activities.

CONCLUSION

Analyzing the results of the work, based on the data laid down in the goal, the following conclusions were made: - Games motivate and amuse students, but can also help them learn by helping them memorize and extract tissue. Recently, the introduction of games has become a well-known technique that is used by almost all teachers in the classroom and advised by methodologists. Our research suggests, in fact, that those students who practice vocabulary games feel more targeted and

interested in what they are actually doing. The cheerful and spontaneous air that accompanies the work during the game promotes student learning. All students showed a desire to effectively explore the lexicographic supply in more fun ways than the classical methods they knew. Finally, our goal was to qualify the effectiveness of the use of vocabulary games in the development of students' communication skills in English language. The result of our research work demonstrates, in fact, that the students were interested in games in general and loved general mass games in the presenter; they made every effort to freeze as favorites. Students collaborated quite actively in games requiring massive work, including humble students. Games should be an obligatory part of the lesson, providing the likelihood of active practice, and at the same time provide great enjoyment for both students and teachers. And we would like to advise the extensive introduction of games to expand students' vocabulary and abilities as a successful method of forming linguistic areas of responsibility.

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